

Integrating Generative AI in Design Education: Metacognitive Patterns in AI-Naive Students

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Abstract—This paper documents an exploratory pedagogical intervention, financed through the ER2Digit European Digital Innovation Hub initiative, integrating Large Language Models into a Service-Design course at the University of Bologna. The study addresses the underexplored challenge of AI literacy development in completely “AI-naive” populations, investigating how fifth-year architecture students with zero prior exposure to generative tools appropriate LLM-based assistants within authentic public administration design projects. The intervention’s original objective of advanced professional integration was radically reformulated into embedded alphabetization when initial assessment revealed students’ complete unfamiliarity with conversational AI interfaces, privacy implications, and foundational mechanisms of probabilistic language generation.

At the mid-point of intervention (week 6/12), preliminary findings reveal one unexpected pattern: intentional friction, where technical failures paradoxically generate deeper understanding of LLM behavior than seamless interactions. Two additional dynamics warrant post-intervention investigation: assessment blind spots in output evaluation, and ethical pragmatism emerging through situated practice. This work-in-progress contributes real-time documentation of AI appropriation under maximal readiness gaps—a context typically excluded from controlled studies but increasingly common in educational institutions.

Index Terms—generative AI, design education, metacognition, cognitive offloading, AI literacy, naive users, service design, pedagogical scaffolding

I. INTRODUCTION

The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) into higher education represents one of the most urgent and complex challenges in contemporary pedagogical practice. While STEM curricula have begun incorporating advanced computational tools, non-STEM disciplines—including social sciences and, in the present case, design—face a dual challenge. Students must acquire proficiency with apparently simple yet deeply complex AI tools while maintaining rigorous epistemological approaches and developing critical competencies that preserve human creativity in increasingly automated contexts. This paper examines these challenges through a specific case study within a regional digital innovation initiative in Italy.

This contribution presents the very preliminary results of a pedagogical intervention carried within the ER2Digit Project, the European Digital Innovation Hub (E-DIH) of Regione Emilia-Romagna. ER2Digit operates as a facilitator of the

transformation process of SMEs and Public Sector Organizations (PSOs). The focus is on the improvement of Public Services, by employing innovative digital solutions. The E-DIH model is supported by the European Commission and Italian Ministero dell’Industria e del Made in Italy; it aims at reducing the digital gap that characterizes the Italian small enterprises and the Public Administration.

In this context, ER2Digit has proposed a call for interest specifically addressed to the non-STEM Departments of the regional Universities. The expected outcomes are the development of “libraries of professional tools based on AI”. The Dipartimento di Architettura dell’Università di Bologna has participated in the call of interest to develop the results in its Corso Magistrale di “Design dei Servizi”. It provides an ideal laboratory for experimenting with the integration of Large Language Models (LLMs) in applied projects.

Nineteen students follow the course. The students are at their last year. The course is devoted to the initial research and prototyping of physical and digital services. ER2Digit support is intended at introducing Generative AI (GenAI) instruments in the project workflow, and eliciting the structure of the library for the specific sector. This year’s focus is on the value generation from PSOs dataset. This peculiar context of last year students unprepared to GenAI instruments, has modified the initial idea of the development of the expected Test-Before-Invest, introducing alphabetization aspects during the presentation.

A. Beyond enthusiasm

Current literature is aware of the threat posed by “cognitive offloading”, and “automation bias” (see II, in the following). These threats appear when using GenAI instruments. University learning contexts are not exempt from these threats. Current research focuses predominantly on STEM students, and lacks systematic understanding of how students engaged in creative projects without technical AI backgrounds can develop critical AI competencies. This is particularly true if they do not have a technical background in AI and they must resort to express complex qualitative judgments.

Addressing these threats in non-STEM contexts requires investigation of three interconnected dimensions:

RT1: What pedagogical methods effectively preserve critical thinking and planning autonomy among AI-naive students?

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RT2: What metrics should be used to evaluate the cognitive process when operating in AI assisted workflows (aside from produced outputs)?

RT3: How to manage the authorship and agency questions to attain pedagogical honesty and professional pragmatism, in the context of the use of AI?

B. Article contribution and structure

The contribution presents the evidence collected during the first half of the intervention in the class. We collected planning discussions, structured prompt logging, students observations. We aim to identify pedagogical emerging patterns that characterize the understanding and use of GenAI instruments, given the alphabetization process in course.

The contribution analyzes the theoretical background in Section II. The ongoing of action intervention is described in Section III, and the preliminary findings are presented in Section IV. The expected theoretical implications are discussed in Section V, focussing on the non-STEM educational context.

Our preliminary analysis at the mid-point of intervention has identified one primary emerging pattern (intentional friction) documented in Section IV, with initial observations on two additional dynamics (assessment challenges and ethical pragmatism) that warrant further investigation. These patterns directly address the research questions posed above. The first pattern is detailed in Section IV. The other two patterns remain preliminary observations requiring further investigation beyond this intervention’s timeframe.

This is a Work in Progress. It offers the unique opportunity to document the “real-time” emerging of required pedagogical practices, in a rapid evolving field, that is the one of the “Pedagogy in the GenAI Era”.

II. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

The integration of generative artificial intelligence systems into educational contexts necessitates rethinking how students develop and apply critical thinking. This section explores three dimensions to understand the pedagogical challenges faced: the cognitive mechanisms through which students delegate mental functions to external tools will be focused; how critical thinking can be assessed when the boundaries between human and computational contributions become blurred and the issues of agency and authorship that arise in human-AI collaborative systems will be overviewed. The opinion here expressed is that these chosen dimensions help understand the pedagogical patterns observed in our training intervention with AI-naive design students.

A. Cognitive offloading and automation bias

The concept of cognitive offloading describes the human tendency to reduce internal cognitive load by transferring part of mental processes to external supports [1]. This evolutionarily advantageous strategy allows us to conserve cognitive resources by delegating tasks to physical or contemporary digital tools. When applied to educational contexts where the primary goal is the development of cognitive skills, cognitive

offloading can generate significant tensions. We identify a “strategic” offloading, when the student maintains conscious control over the process, versus “default” offloading, when delegation becomes uncritical.

The phenomenon of automation bias, defined by [2], is closely related to offloading: it is the tendency to favor suggestions generated by automated systems even when they are incorrect or suboptimal. In the educational context, this bias is relevant: students, especially those with less experience in the domain, tend to overestimate the accuracy of outputs generated by AI perceived as “authoritative” [3]. Research in educational technology has documented how students exposed to automated tutoring systems develop dependence on the answers provided, thus reducing their autonomous cognitive effort [4].

In the context of education for service design, these phenomena appear to take on particular connotations. Design thinking is characterized by its generative and abductive nature, where the quality of the exploratory process (including dead ends and iterations) is an integral part of learning [5]. Design requires tolerance of ambiguity and the ability to navigate ill-defined problem spaces. The introduction of LLMs that quickly generate seemingly complete solutions risks short-circuiting this exploratory process. This happens when LLMs replacing the productive struggle [6] with premature convergence toward “good enough” outputs.

The pedagogical challenge is therefore twofold: on the one hand, recognizing the potential value of LLMs as cognitive scaffolding tools that can extend students’ design capabilities; on the other hand, preserving the “cognitive friction” necessary for the development of metacognitive skills and independent judgment. For AI-naive students this tension is amplified by the absence of previous references to critically understand the capabilities and limitations of the tools. A fundamental knowledge gap thus emerges: the choice of the pedagogical mechanisms allowing critical thinking to remain active when using generative tools that drastically reduce the cognitive costs of production.

B. Assessment of critical thinking in AI era

Pre-AI assessment frameworks in design training could be focused on output-based metrics: the aesthetic and functional quality of the final product, the consistency of the solution with the requirements, and the presentation of the concept [7]. This approach becomes radically inadequate when outputs are partially or totally mediated by AI systems capable of generating visually sophisticated artifacts regardless of the student’s design understanding.

There is a need to shift the evaluative focus from the *product* to the *process*. That is, “how” and “why” the student has produced her work and made certain design decisions, what role the AI tool had in these decisions, and the level of critical awareness in its use. This shift necessarily requires qualitative methodologies capable of accessing the “black box” of design reasoning. Some of these are think-aloud protocols, semi-

structured interviews, analysis of interaction patterns with tools [8].

In the presented context of AI-naive students this procedural focus becomes potentially critical. It cannot be assumed that students possess mental frameworks for critically interpreting the capabilities of the tools; these frameworks must be constructed through experience of use accompanied by explicit reflection. The knowledge gap that our experience is stimulating us to address therefore is: how can we make the quality of the cognitive process observable and assessable when the tangible output is mediated by AI?

C. Distributed cognition and co-authorship

The theory of distributed cognition conceptualizes cognition as a process distributed across individuals, artifacts, and the environment. In this perspective, cognitive tools are not simply passive “means” but active participants in the cognitive system: the navigator who plots a course on a nautical chart is not simply “using” the tool, but thinking *through* and *with* the tool in a hybrid cognitive configuration. Hollan [9] extends this framework to computational artifacts, showing how human cognition is already intrinsically technologically mediated.

However, the introduction of generative AI systems introduces a qualitative discontinuity with respect to traditional cognitive tools. Clark [10] distinguishes between tools that “amplify” existing human capabilities and tools that “transform” the very nature of the cognitive task. LLMs seem to operate in the latter category: LLMs do not merely speed up or facilitate operations that the student could perform independently, but generate outputs that could exceed both quantitatively and qualitatively what the student would produce without assistance. This raises fundamental questions of agency and authorship: who is the actual author of a design concept generated iteratively in dialogue with an LLM? Where does creative agency lie in this process?

For our AI-naive students these ambiguities are experienced with particular intensity. Without established regulatory references or technical expertise to understand “what AI is doing,” students navigate *gray areas of authorship*. They may implicitly develop norms of use that may diverge significantly from institutional or professional expectations. The knowledge gap then becomes: how can we support students in building ethical frameworks for managing agency and authorship in human-AI collaborations, when they themselves are simultaneously learning both the domain (design) and the tool (AI)?

These three theoretical dimensions—cognitive offloading, process assessment, and distributed agency—form the analytical lens through which a complete study should examine our pedagogical intervention. In the following section, we describe the methodological approach used to investigate the first one, i.e. how AI-naive design students navigate the challenges in practice, allowing critical thinking to remain active when using generative tools.

III. METHODOLOGY

Given the intervention’s ongoing nature (week 6 of ~12), alphabetization context, and absence of control groups, Sec-

tion III-E explicitly addresses the methodological constraints inherent to real-time documentation of pedagogical adaptation.

The pedagogical intervention that is the subject of this study arises from two opportunities. On the one hand, funding for the ER2Digit project through the call for proposals “Developing generative AI solutions in the humanities, economics, and social sciences” requires to develop a technology-neutral approach to the operational integration of GenAI tools into an existing curriculum. On the other hand, the preliminary assessment revealed an unexpected educational paradox: fifth-year students in a Non-STEM-oriented course had no basic literacy in large language models and were completely unaware of the existence of tools such as Claude, ChatGPT, or NotebookLM, as well as technical infrastructures such as Ollama or the privacy and security implications of using cloud platforms.

A radical revision of the initial approach was thus required. What had been conceived as an advanced integration of LLMs into established design practices became an alphabetization experiment, where students learned AI fundamentals while simultaneously applying these tools to authentic projects. This forced pedagogical pivot—both a constraint and an opportunity—meant that our methodological design evolved iteratively rather than following a predetermined protocol. The challenge is further complicated by a structural time misalignment: the seminars on AI are being delivered in the same time frame when students are already in the advanced creative phase of their service design projects for public bodies. In this context, this time constraint, initially perceived as problematic, has revealed itself as an opportunity to observe how theoretical knowledge is retroactively integrated into processes already underway, generating what appear to be peculiar forms of instrumental appropriation.

A. Participants and Prerequisites

The nineteen students (see Section I) are organized into six project groups (teams), each engaged in the development of digital services for different regional public administration bodies: the topic was chosen by the group, and the aim was to bring value to the PSOs collected data. The initial assessment, conducted through informal interviews during the second week, documented a complete lack of prior experience in the use of GenAI tools. This AI-naive starting condition was confirmed by operational evidence: the students encountered basic technical difficulties during the login and account configuration phase, and all of them were unaware of basic issues related to privacy and data security in interactions with cloud platforms.

To standardize the technological infrastructure and ensure uniform access conditions, each student received a dedicated Claude Pro account, segregated through “disposable” email addresses created specifically for the course. This choice made it possible to control exposure to specific platform features and collect comparable data on interactions, while minimizing the risks associated with sharing sensitive project data outside the laboratory domain.

B. Design of the Pedagogical Intervention

The intervention is structured in a series of workshops spread over approximately twelve weeks of the course, for an estimated total of eighteen to twenty hours of direct training, integrated into the regular teaching curriculum. The pedagogical structure does not follow a traditional linear progression but adopts what we define as a “Learning by Stumbling” — a pedagogical hypothesis. This pedagogical hypothesis—that systematic transformation of errors into learning opportunities would generate deeper understanding—remained to be validated through the intervention itself. Whether this reframing effectively generated deeper learning remains an empirical question addressed in Section IV.

The first workshop in the second week introduced the fundamental mechanisms of Large Language Models through the metaphor of multidimensional maps and semantic embeddings. A large amount of time has been devoted to the security issues, and to the demystification of the “Intelligence” naming. During the second session the application of the P-C-T-F (Purpose-Context-Task-Format) framework derived from [11] for structuring prompts was introduced. In this first session, it was decided to use three specially designed practice projects to allow experimentation in a protected environment, where failure had no consequences on actual deliverables. Presentations on these practice projects (mentioned in Section III-D) serve as baseline assessment of initial skill development, though comparative analysis with later work remains pending. Students were organized into initial super-groups, temporarily aggregating two teams to facilitate mutual technical support during a phase of maximum operational fragility.

This second workshop accompanied the exploratory research phase of the real projects, introducing prompt techniques for structured research of public administration data sources. An iterative triplet system was introduced, where each initial prompt was followed by a second-order critical prompt and cross-validation among team members, with mandatory role rotation to prevent those who generated the output from also being responsible for its validation. This structure was designed to prevent default cognitive offloading by forcing metacognitive awareness of AI-generated outputs. However, as documented in Section IV, the internalization of this practice proved more challenging than anticipated, with students requiring ongoing facilitator intervention throughout the observation period rather than adopting it as an autonomous workflow.

The third workshop in the sixth week focused on insight discovery and the Critic approach to the solution, exploring the use of Claude both as a facilitator and as a threat generator. Students were required to document their preliminary design decisions on paper before engaging with Claude, then explicitly compare their initial thinking with AI-influenced directions. This analog checkpoint was intended to make visible the divergence between human intention and algorithmic interpretation, though its effectiveness as a metacognitive scaffold remained to be assessed. The pedagogical progression follows a deliberate path from zero-shot prompts to few-shot

structures and finally to embryonic forms of Chain-of-Thought reasoning, in parallel with the increase in design complexity.

C. Multi-Level Data Collection

Data collection is structured through a dedicated digital infrastructure that includes a website with NextCloud components for file sharing and DokuWiki for the collaborative construction of a knowledge base. Students can draw from a glossary of terminology, and they are encouraged to progressively enrich it during the course. The glossary is intended as a shared artifact to stabilize the common technical language. Workshop presentations and support materials are made permanently accessible through this platform (in Italian).

The documentation system is based on progressively evolved Excel templates. The first version of the log prompts, distributed during the research phase, required basic recording of the objective, prompt used, and output received. The second version adds a mandatory section on corrective actions taken when the output is deemed inadequate. The third version, not yet in use, will prompt the explanation of the strategic choices underlying each interaction.

The dataset is currently being collected. It includes complete conversations with Claude exported by individual teams, structured prompt logs, field notes of classroom observations during workshops and independent work sessions, and presentations by super-groups on practice projects that serve as a baseline for assessing skill development. Given the ongoing nature of the intervention, the dataset has significant structural limitations: post-course interviews scheduled for the end of the semester are missing, final project deliverables are not yet available, and any form of longitudinal assessment beyond the three-month course is currently impossible. These constraints mean that findings in Section IV represent preliminary observations of emerging patterns rather than conclusive assessments of pedagogical efficacy. The documentation system captures real-time appropriation dynamics but cannot yet evaluate whether observed patterns persist, deepen, or transform as students gain additional experience.

D. Analytical Framework

The analysis of the collected data adopts a mixed-methods approach with a qualitative bias. The coding has three analytical levels: explicit patterns identifiable in teaching materials and student verbalizations, implicit patterns emerging from systematic behaviors that are not consciously articulated, and divergent patterns that signal contradictions between what is said and what is done. The coding process proceeds iteratively through initial line-by-line coding of transcripts and logs, focused coding to aggregate codes into thematic categories, and theoretical coding to identify relationships between categories and construct interpretive hypotheses. Students are required to engage in continuous memo-writing, documenting analytical choices and moments of theoretical sampling where additional data are specifically sought to confirm or disconfirm emerging hypotheses.

The quantitative component is being drafted to descriptive metrics of progression, such as the frequency of use of different types of prompts over time or the index of deviation from the templates provided, without inferential ambitions given the sample size.

The rigor criteria are qualitatively evaluated: credibility through member checking with the course instructor and triangulation between multiple data sources; transferability through thick description of the context and experimental conditions; dependability by a complete audit trail of methodological decisions; confirmability through explicit declaration of the researcher’s position as an internal facilitator of the training process.

The methodology described generates the dataset supporting the preliminary patterns discussed in Section IV. Our analysis explores whether and how the AI-naive population, temporal misalignment, and Learning by Stumbling approach may have influenced students’ appropriation of GenAI tools. Early observations suggest forms of partial and situated appropriation that challenge assumptions about optimal integration timelines, though definitive conclusions about pedagogical effectiveness must await course completion and longitudinal assessment.

E. Methodological Limitations and Study Constraints

Several methodological constraints require explicit acknowledgment. First, the alphabetization context meant that pedagogical interventions evolved iteratively in response to student needs rather than following a rigidly pre-specified protocol. This adaptive flexibility, while pedagogically necessary, complicates systematic evaluation of specific intervention effects.

Second, the ongoing nature of the study means that patterns documented in Section IV represent preliminary observations of emerging dynamics rather than stable, conclusive findings. Post-intervention interviews, final deliverables, and any longitudinal assessment beyond the semester remain unavailable.

Third, the absence of control groups and the small sample size ($n=19$) constrain generalizability and prevent causal attribution. We cannot definitively isolate whether observed patterns result from our specific pedagogical structures, the AI-naive starting condition, the temporal misalignment, or other contextual factors.

Fourth, the researcher’s dual role as both course facilitator and data analyst introduces potential observer bias, though we attempt to mitigate this through triangulation across multiple data sources and explicit positioning statements.

These limitations are not methodological failures but inherent features of real-time documentation of emergency pedagogical adaptation. As the Conclusions elaborate, this study’s distinctive contribution lies precisely in capturing appropriation dynamics under conditions of maximal readiness gaps—circumstances that controlled studies typically exclude but that many educational institutions currently face.

IV. FINDINGS

Analysis of the data collected through interaction at the present stage of the intervention reveals one main pattern in

the appropriation of GenAI tools by a population with no prior literacy. The pattern appears to emerge from a complex process of negotiation between project expectations, perceived technological affordances, and situated cognitive constraints. The primary pattern identified directly addresses RT1 regarding cognitive offloading, while preliminary observations touch on RT2 and RT3 discussed in the previous section, illuminating how the construct of cognitive offloading manifests concretely in educational contexts where initial technological ignorance is the norm rather than the exception.

A. Intentional Friction

This pattern, emerged from the classroom observations, concerns the counterintuitive relationship between difficulty of use and meaningful learning. Contrary to the expectations, AI-naive students developed a deeper understanding of LLM mechanisms precisely through repeated experiences of technical failures and inadequate outputs. The students themselves classify the first generated interactions as “unusable” or “out of context.” These failures trigger iterative cycles of progressively more sophisticated reformulation. Here, the understanding of the model’s probabilistic behavior emerges inductively from practical experience rather than deductively from theoretical instruction. Students applied the P-C-T-F framework.

This pattern connects directly to the concept of cognitive offloading discussed in the theoretical background, but complicates it significantly. The AI-naive population in this study demonstrated that premature or unconscious offloading can be counterproductive. Students who attempted to delegate complex design tasks to Claude without first developing a basic understanding of the model’s capabilities and limitations consistently perceived lower-quality output than those who initially maintained a more conservative and incremental approach. The analysis of the field notes will give further insights in this direction.

The notion of “intentional friction” thus emerges as an unplanned pedagogical principle. The mandatory analog checkpoints introduced in the third workshop, initially conceived as a safety measure to avoid uncritical dependence on AI, appeared to function as a generative mechanism of metacognition. These checkpoints made visible the divergences between human intention and algorithmic interpretation, transforming each interaction into an opportunity for meta-reflective learning. Post-intervention data will clarify whether group reports confirm that the moments of greatest learning coincide with situations in which Claude’s output “does not understand what we want,” forcing them to reformulate not only the prompt but the very conceptualization of the design problem.

With respect to RT1, presently the friction demonstrates how cognitive offloading in AI-naive contexts is not a linear process of lightening the cognitive load but a complex renegotiation of boundaries between internal and external mental work, where the initial resistance of the tool paradoxically functions as a pedagogical affordance. Beyond cognitive offloading patterns, preliminary observations suggest emerging dynamics in assessment capabilities and ethical awareness.

B. Assessment Blind Spot and Ethical Pragmatism

With respect to RT2, evidence from mid-term interviews suggests difficulty in distinguishing between factual correctness, contextual appropriateness, and stylistic quality of outputs. Students appear to collapse these dimensions into simplistic judgment of “good/bad.” A dialogic interaction with the LLM rather than an “algorithmic” interaction does not emerge, yet.

With respect to the last pattern, until now, privacy has not arisen as an issue. An analysis of the notes may be more specific at the end of the semester. However, conversations make evident that account segregation through dedicated emails, designed as a technical containment measure, proved insufficient in the face of practices that are unaware of the implications of the terms of service of cloud platforms. Findings suggest that ethical AI literacy cannot be transmitted abstractly in advance but must be constructed through situated experience. Presently, evidence with respect to RT3 supports the idea that declarative ethical codes may be ineffective for AI-naive populations, requiring scenarios where dilemmas are encountered, discussed collectively, and transformed into emerging operating principles.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The findings are emerging not as planned research outcomes but as observable byproducts of emergency alphabetization under institutional constraints, constituting both the study’s primary limitation and its distinctive contribution. The forced pedagogical pivot from advanced integration to basic literacy illuminates metacognitive dynamics typically invisible in studies assuming pre-existing digital fluency. The intervention’s in-progress nature precludes longitudinal assessment and causal attribution, while the absence of control groups and limited sample size constrain generalizability. However, this methodologically imperfect documentation offers rare empirical evidence of appropriation dynamics when the gap between technological expectations and actual competencies is maximal, suggesting that GenAI integration in unprepared student populations may require significantly extended timeframes, metacognitive scaffolding, and pedagogical mediation than current literature anticipates.

This work-in-progress will reach completion in February. The complete dataset will enable validation and extension of preliminary patterns, with the following completion plan:

Intentional Friction (RT1): Systematic coding of field notes will quantify facilitator intervention frequency across workshop progression. Analysis of exported conversations will measure prompt sophistication evolution through automated metrics (length, specificity, P-C-T-F framework adherence).

Assessment Capabilities (RT2): Post-intervention semi-structured interviews will probe students’ ability to distinguish factual correctness, contextual appropriateness, and stylistic quality. Member checking will validate observed assessment difficulties.

Ethical Pragmatism (RT3): Final deliverable analysis will document authorship attribution practices. Follow-up questionnaire will assess internalized ethical frameworks.

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